

Overcoming the Risks:

Can the Addition of Yoga, Mindfulness and Meditation
in UK Prisons Help to Tackle Reoffending?

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Abstract

The use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation within prison to aid in the reduction of recidivism is a limited but evolving area within criminological research. HM Prison Service provides methods of rehabilitation to its offenders with the intention of reducing reoffending rates, although the recidivism rate in the UK is one of the highest among western nations. Scandinavian prisons utilise alternative methods of rehabilitation, such as yoga, mindfulness and meditation which may be a contributing factor to the low rates of recidivism in Nordic countries. This research report aims to understand the consequences of incarceration upon a prison population that already present distinct deprivations and how yoga may aid in the rehabilitation of these deprivations to ultimately tackle reoffending. Utilising secondary data analysis in the form of a literature-based approach, this research made use of journal articles, official statistics and academic research to achieve its objectives. This report specifically aims to understand the population to which this research pertains to by considering the official statistics that underpin criminogenic behaviours, the consequences of imprisonment, the costs of rehabilitation and how yoga, mindfulness and meditation helps to alleviate risk factors to aid in the reduction of recidivism. The report found that yogic practices in prisons may hold a basis in rehabilitative theories such as the Good Lives Model and Desistance theory by changing the perspective of an offender to eventually desist from crime. By compiling research that supports existing studies that propose yoga may be beneficial for the prison population to help to tackle reoffending, this report suggests that yoga may yield considerable benefits for this population in terms of addressing the risks a prisoner may present. These findings can be observed to improve rehabilitation in the prison system in the UK, although further analysis on this topic is advised.

Contents Page

Acknowledgements	1
Abstract	2
Contents Page	3
Chapter 1: Introduction	5
Chapter 2: The UK Prison Context & The Potential of Yoga	9
2.1 The UK's Prison Populace: A Statistical Overview.....	9
2.1.1 Incarceration and Recidivism.....	9
2.1.2 Drug Misuse.....	9
2.1.3 Educational Needs.....	10
2.1.4 Unemployment.....	10
2.2 What is Yoga, Mindfulness and Meditation?.....	11
2.2.1 Yoga.....	11
2.2.2 Mindfulness.....	12
2.2.3 Meditation.....	12
2.3. Consequences of Incarceration	13
2.3.1 Mental Health.....	14
2.3.2 Physical Health	14
2.3.3 Overcrowding.....	15
2.4 Effects of Yoga, Mindfulness & Meditation	15
2.4.1 Yoga and the Physical.....	16
2.4.2 Yoga and the Psychological	16
2.4.3 Yoga and Substance Abuse.....	17
Chapter 3: Comparing Rehabilitation Programmes	18
3.1 Methods of Rehabilitation in Prison	18
3.1.1 Offending Behaviour Programmes	18
3.1.2 Scandinavia & Rehabilitation	19
3.2 And the Costs?.....	20
3.2.1 Cost of Imprisonment.....	20
3.2.2 Cost of Reoffending.....	20
3.2.3 Cost of Rehabilitation	21
3.3 Yoga in Correctional Settings.....	22

3.3.1 A Summary of Past Prison Yoga Studies	22
3.3.2 Prison Yoga from the Inside.....	24
Chapter 4: Conclusion.....	26
List of Figures	28
References	29

Chapter 1: Introduction

The notion of a prison is of relative modernity, with its foundations in Western Europe and the United States reaching across the world partly due to colonial growth (Coyle, 2005). Prior to the Prison Act 1898, which affirmed reformation as the main function of a prison, prisons were simply places where individuals were sent to await trial or more arbitrary punishments such as whipping or the death penalty, whose purposes were to deter and shame the perpetrator (Howard League for Penal Reform, 2003). In more recent times, the use of prison is often the most severe punishment available for a judicial body to impose, with the purpose of a prison viewed as a means of protection for the public, working to prevent future victims of crime, whilst addressing the fundamental causes of offending and reoffending by promoting the reform and rehabilitation of an offender (Ministry of Justice, 2021). However, prisons in the United Kingdom have a poor history in terms of the prevention of reoffending, with around 70% of offenders reoffending once released from prison, irrespective of the application of tougher sentences and stricter laws and legislations to tackle reoffending (Opperman, 2014).

As such, the notion of combatting recidivism by way of rehabilitation in prisons has been a cause for concern for governmental bodies due to high reoffending rates amongst offenders upon release, with its aim to tackle the cycle of reoffending by implementing rehabilitative methods (Ministry of Justice, 2013). Rehabilitation, for the purposes of this research report may be defined as aiding in the change of an individual's behaviour by the deployment of interventions to remove the tendency, desire or requirement to offend (Robinson and Crow, 2009). Despite the efforts and ambitions of the state to use penal systems to reform and rehabilitate its' offenders, there is evidence to suggest that this institution in the UK is failing to implement successful rehabilitative practices (Bullock and Bunce, 2020). This then poses the question, what else might work when tackling the problem of reoffending? In the expanding arena of comparative criminology and criminal justice, Nordic countries have been used as a comparison for penal regimes globally, with the Nordic Exceptionalism thesis claiming that Nordic or Scandinavian countries maintain a more humane approach to penal control, rooted in the differing notions of welfare and social solidity (Barker, 2012). Nordic countries, such as Sweden and Norway, utilise alternative therapeutic methods as a form of rehabilitation for their offenders (Cornell, 2022), to which this research report will delve into the idea that the use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation, imparted in Scandinavian prisons, and various prisons around the world, may be more effective in the rehabilitation of offenders than methods of rehabilitation already in place in UK prisons. Yogic practice in prisons may hold some efficacy for this populace as evidence suggests a positive effect on risk factors

linked with recidivism (Sfendla et al. 2018). As the French philosopher Michel Foucault (1926 – 1984) suggested, punishment experienced a shift, from the punishing of the body to the disciplining of the soul (Foucault, 2019). If this is to be taken literally, then one's soul may experience punishment but also unification between the mind, the body and the soul, which is what yoga, mindfulness and meditation seeks to achieve (Kumar and Nitin, 2021), implying a valuable and optimistic place for yogic practice in the prison system.

Theories relating to rehabilitation and recidivism have long been used within the field of criminology to attempt to provide theoretical justifications. Theories are explanations that make an effort to explain crime and criminal behaviours, that in contemporary society, may mirror the prevailing ideals of the present social world, reflecting the cultural, political and economic advancements of the modern era (Hopkins Burke, 2019). In terms of theories of offending and reoffending, the Good Lives Model, initially developed by Tony Ward (2002) may be reflected upon when considering offender rehabilitation. The Good Lives Model suggests that rehabilitation can be achieved when basing this upon the notion that all individuals are goal orientated, living in accordance with their primary human goods or experiences to increase the individual's happiness, spirituality or creativity among others (Chu et al. 2014). From the perspective of the Good Lives Model, an offender may commit a criminal act to achieve their happiness through any means available to them, often through socially unacceptable means (Fortune, 2014). The Good Lives Model holds a strong developmental and historical basis, emphasising continuity between the 'old' criminal self and the creation of a new self (Ward et al. 2007), enabling an offender to achieve their goals whilst attempting to manage the risks of reoffending they may pose (Thakker et al. 2013). In addition, a rehabilitative theory known as Desistance theory, in a general sense, identifies rehabilitation as the process of an individual gradually moving away from a lifestyle of offending, with considerations that an individual might reshape their identity in developing a life free of crime (Szifris et al. 2018). This means that the process of desistance from criminal behaviours involves a cognitive shift, requiring an individual to build a meaningful perception of their future self while imprisoned, which does however, hinge upon structural opportunities that an individual can benefit from (Szifris et al. 2018), which as this research will portray, are of limited access to a prisoner. With an understanding of the theoretical frameworks underpinning rehabilitation and recidivism, one can begin to examine ways to tackle reoffending, beginning in UK prisons.

It is the purpose of this research to measure the potential for accredited and required use of yoga in prisons, but one must first become familiar with the population this research pertains to and the current leading methods of rehabilitation in the UK and its costs. This dissertation will therefore explore just

that, in conjunction with the potential benefits of yoga, mindfulness and meditation upon the consequential features of imprisonment and finally, the exploration of a summary of past studies within prisons that have each investigated the use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation upon a more complex populace with a multitude of criminogenic needs, all with the aim of using this practice within UK prisons to aid in the reduction of reoffending.

A literature-based approach was taken for this research report to answer the question of whether the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation might be employed in UK prisons to help to tackle reoffending. This involved the analysis of secondary data to support or disprove this hypothesis. Secondary data analysis is the evaluation of data that has already been collected and is readily available (Clark et al. 2021). The use of secondary data is advantageous to this report since the costs of analysis of secondary data is low (Cheng and Phillips, 2014). Furthermore, secondary data and analysis offers access to a considerable quantity of information and saves a researcher time instead of spending time gathering primary data (Hagan, 2013). In addition, using secondary data affords a researcher access to high quality and large quantities of data which, for the most part, have been collated by funded agencies or studies (Johnston, 2014). On the other hand, secondary data analysis may present some limitations too. An absence of familiarity with the existing data collected is one of these limitations (Clark, et al. 2021). To confront this drawback, a substantial amount of time was set aside to become acquainted with the data obtained. Moreover, the secondary data analysis approach presents a well-recognised limitation, in that the initial data was collected for another purpose, that is to say, the data was not collected to answer this specific research question (Johnston, 2014), meaning that a researcher will thus be reliant upon the interpretation of the data offered by the initial researcher (Denscombe, 2021). This method was selected for use by this research project since conducting primary research on the topic in question may require a longitudinal study and due to the relatively constrictive nature of an undergraduate dissertation (Clark et al. 2021), this project simply does not have the time necessary to add to the findings of the literature currently available by way of primary research. Secondly, conducting secondary analysis allowed for access to data regarding the efficacy of yogic practice in prisons in other countries that might not have otherwise been available with another method of research. Secondary research in the form of past studies were vital for this research report as they provided a valuable perspective to support the effectiveness of yoga, mindfulness and meditation practices upon the prison population. As all of the past studies cited in this research project conducted primary research to find the outcome to their hypothesis, this allowed this report to gain an accurate, evidence-based understanding of the results which is crucial to finding the answer to its own hypothesis (Denscombe, 2021). While the sample sizes of the studies and testimonials used are rather small, they

will show a positive stance on how the use of yoga in UK prisons might aid in the reduction of reoffending.

The decision to include the studies reported was made initially by searching for academic sources specifically relevant to the use of yogic practice and its effects upon prisoners, to which this research found the most prominence of yogic practice in prison in Nordic countries. Secondly, the data was of high quality, in that the studies were all from credible, recent, academic sources and all used similar methods of research, producing quantitative findings (Denscombe, 2021). The problem this research encountered was a lack of volume of studies within the field regarding the use of yoga in prisons, that is to say, there has not been a vast amount of research in this area (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016), meaning there were not many, if any sources that suggested yogic practice in prisons was unattainable, thus this research report's want for a balanced argument was a touch forgone. This means that this research project is basing its conclusions upon the findings of the studies cited, all of which had very small sample sizes, indicating the crucial need for more research within this field before yogic practice might be employed in UK prisons to help to reduce recidivism.

Ethical principles and access issues are a serious and multifaceted component of any investigation carried out in the field of Sociology or Criminology (Johnstone, 2005). A code of ethics or guiding principles consider the morality or moral principles emphasised in any research that might be undertaken, guiding a researcher in ensuring that no harm will come to any party involved in the research (Crowther-Dowey and Fussey, 2013). As this research project relies heavily upon the literature available within this field, this project will seek to use studies that have obtained ethical approval for their research (Denscombe, 2021) and sources and statistics that have shared their findings in an accurate and honest way (British Sociological Association, 2017). In following an ethical code, this research report will seek to cite all research materials used accurately and will not claim any works by another researcher as its own (British Society of Criminology Statement of Ethics, 2015).

Chapter 2: The UK Prison Context & The Potential of Yoga

2.1 A Statistical Overview of the UK's Prison Populace

To gain an understanding of whether the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation might be employed in UK prisons to rehabilitate offenders, thus reducing recidivism, one must first understand the population to which this research pertains. This research report will explore this population in three subcategories and statistically, to gain a quantitative overview of the prison populace. One must acknowledge the scale of the prison population and those who have reoffended, with the intention of gaining insight into the common socioeconomic factors of said population.

2.1.1 Incarceration & Recidivism

The rate of reoffending in England and Wales in 2020/2021 was 25.6%, this percentage at its lowest in 10 years compared to the percentage of offenders who reoffended in 2010/2011, which stood at 31.6% (Clark, 2022). In England and Wales, there are approximately 80,660 prisoners, Scotland holds 7,430 prisoners and Northern Ireland has 1,640 prisoners, totalling approximately 89,520 people, these figures encompassing men, women and children (Sturge, 2022). This figure is higher than that of the previous year, to which the Ministry of Justice (2021) ascertain that there were 78,756 prisoners in the UK in September 2021. The prison population doubled between 1993 and 2012 in England and Wales, with instant custodial sentences accounting for most of the rise between 1993 and 2020 (Ministry of Justice, 2020) and this population is projected to increase to 98,500 by March 2026 (Ministry of Justice, 2021). To put these figures into perspective, there are 159 prisoners per 100,000 of the national population in England and Wales, 162 prisoners per 100,000 in Scotland and 97 per 100,000 in Northern Ireland (Sturge, 2022). This is comparable with prisoner populations in countries such as Sweden, who's prison systems are very different to that of the UK, where there are 74 prisoners per 100,000 of the national population (World Prison Brief, 2022). In addition, Norway, who's prison system is very similar to that of Sweden, have a reoffending rate of 20% which is among the lowest percentage of this type in western nations (Aidoo, 2016), suggesting that the differences in rehabilitation in prisons between the aforementioned Nordic countries and the UK are of substantial significance.

2.1.2 Drug Misuse

There are several well-established factors that may affect the offending and the reoffending behaviours of the prison population; drug misuse has a significant relation to the causes of reoffending. There is

evidence to show that 41% of prisoners reported that they committed offences solely for the purposes of buying drugs, with one year conviction rates standing at more than double for offenders who used drugs in a four-week period prior to custodial sentences, at 62% (O'Hagan and Hardwick, 2017). In prison, there were 53,193 adults enrolled in drugs and alcohol treatments in 2018/2019, with approximately 65% of this number starting treatment in the same year of incarceration, however, the total number of adults in treatment fell by 4% in 2018 to 2019 in contrast to the previous year (Public Health England, 2020). A total of 30,882 offenders left treatments for drug and alcohol misuse within that year with just over a quarter or 27% leaving treatment free from the dependence of substances (Public Health England, 2020). This suggests that the rehabilitative attempts made by UK prisons to reform offenders and reduce recidivism may fail due to a drug or alcohol dependency (Opperman, 2014).

2.1.3 Educational Needs

Of the approximate number of 89,520 prisoners currently held in the UK, a vast majority of this populace lack basic educational skills which may, at least in part, be an explanation for offending and reoffending behaviours. The condition of education in prisons is poor, with 60% of prisons graded inadequate or requiring improvement in terms of education, skills and work in the last five years (Ofsted and Spielman, 2021). Of the UK's prison population, 47% have no formal educational qualifications, 42% of those incarcerated have been excluded or expelled from schools and 57% of adult prisoners who took initial assessments (to pinpoint the knowledge or skills of an offender) had a literacy level below the expectations of an 11-year-old (Ofsted and Spielman, 2021). With educational options in place for prisoners as one method of rehabilitation and reduction of reoffending, a relatively small number took part in courses of this nature, at 49,855 of those incarcerated, 39,419 of this number participated in courses below that of level 2 or GCSE level accreditation (Ministry of Justice, 2022). The UK government places educational needs in the bracket of reform, which seeks to measure the attainment of prisoners while in custody, however, placing an emphasis on qualifications achieved may encourage contributors to produce lower quality, shorter educational courses, with reform becoming of secondary prevalence (Ellison et al. 2017).

2.1.4 Unemployment

Further to educational needs, the role of unemployment and poverty has been a longstanding factor in the explanation of criminal offending and reoffending, where those who have prior offences face considerable challenges when pursuing employment (Fox et al. 2021) and those who had previously offended were more likely than not to reoffend if they had a combination of both employment and accommodation demands (Ministry of Justice, 2012). Of the UK's prison populace, just 17% succeed in

getting a job within a year of their release, with those who have previously offended being up to 9% less likely to reoffend (Ministry of Justice, 2020). Those who have been previously incarcerated experienced a wage gap of approximately £60 per month, where an ex-offender still faced reduced wages after five years of employment (Stacy, 2015). In prison, an average of 793 prisoners engaged in work inside prison walls each month, an increase of 78% from the previous year's figure of 445 (Ministry of Justice, 2022). As employment is a tool that is said to better the chances of reducing recidivism, it stands to reason that an offender would be less likely to reoffend if they are engaged in better paid, steady work (Panditharatna, 2020).

With this statistical overview in mind, it can be said that there is a crucial need to adjust what offenders do in prison, as prisoners who do not participate in rehabilitative methods including vocational training and education are more likely to reoffend once released (Opperman, 2014).

2.2 What is Yoga, Mindfulness & Meditation?

To understand whether the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation might be employed in UK prisons as an official method of rehabilitation to help to combat reoffending, one must first understand what the principles of yoga, mindfulness and meditation are. These notions can be understood separately, although it is wise to note that mindfulness and meditation are key elements of the practice of yoga (Derlic, 2020) and are to be thought of, more often than not, as one unified practice.

2.2.1 Yoga

Yoga is a traditional, ancient and spiritual practice of Indian origin (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). Ancient practitioners used yoga as a way to explore the exterior world and the individual interior, benefitting from yoga, not as a religious practice, but as a way of life (Garfinkel and Schumacher Jr, 2000). The etymological origin of yoga is the Sanskrit word 'yuj' which means 'to join' (Newcombe, 2009), although modernity has come to understand the word yoga to mean the unification of discipline, joining the mind and body to the self or one's soul (Garfinkel and Schumacher Jr, 2000). In today's modern world, three essential elements, or ethical standards, are observed within a yoga practice, which are postures (asanas), control of the breath (pranayama) and meditation (dhyana) (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). Those who practice yoga pull their attention to the present moment with the use of breathing and movement, emptying the mind, letting go of tension in the body and non-judgmentally drawing attention to self (Derlic, 2020). These elements are not enough to incite change or healing alone, albeit key factors, one must observe the foundations to which these elements derive where

there is a need to intertwine discipline and concentration to aid in healing and change (Derlic, 2020), notions of which each relate to the Good Lives Model and Desistance theories of rehabilitation.

Figure 1. Image to show asana poses (from Bilderbeck et al. 2013).

2.2.2 Mindfulness

Mindfulness can be recognised as the ability to become less reactive to occurrences in the present moment (Germer, 2004). It is a manner of being and a way of linking to one's experiences, incorporating the awareness of being in a caring, open and understanding way (Shapiro et al. 2015). Practicing mindfulness means homing in on the ability to see reality clearly so one may respond effectively, imparting the intention to do so by reflecting on our values or motivations, whilst paying attention to the moments we experience and with an attitude of acceptance and with an open heart (Shapiro et al. 2015). Essentially, mindfulness can be considered as a tool to train the mind, with beginnings in monasteries (Russell, 2017) and promoted in the spiritual and religious establishments from Eastern territories, such as Hinduism and Buddhism (Selva, 2017). In more modern times, mindfulness has been tailored to the western world as a method of stress alleviation called Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR), which may be used to relieve stress, treat anxiety and even treat addiction to drugs (Joseph and Crichlow, 2015).

2.2.3 Meditation

Meditation, therefore, may be defined as the practice of fostering mindfulness (Germer, 2004), that is to say, meditation can be seen as practices of many forms that exercise awareness and attention with

the intention of cultivating spiritual and psychological well-being and development (Shapiro et al. 2003). Meditation is not just one specific technique, rather it is a term that integrates a range of various techniques (Matko et al. 2021), which include focus on concentration, awareness of the breath, a mantra or an object (Hunnicutt and Rhodes, 2015). The aim of mindfulness meditation is not to alter the thoughts of an individual, rather to develop a different connection to one's thoughts and feelings (Auty et al. 2015). Like mindfulness, meditation has been established from Eastern traditions with a documented history that stretches back more than thousands of years (Manocha, 2000). Types of meditation include transcendental meditation, which can initially be explained as the thinking of a mantra (a repeated word or sound) then focussing one's attention when the mantra is forgotten as a way of exploring inner silence (Travis and Parim, 2017), and Vipassana meditation, a meditation practice that involves the objective observation of the physical sensations in the body, incorporating the breath to encourage concentration (Krygier et al. 2013).

When yoga, mindfulness and meditation are entwined, for yoga as a practice is incomplete without the incorporation of mindful activity and meditative condition (Derlic, 2020), the practice yields some physical and mental benefits which can be used to incite change within an individual. This dissertation will herein refer to the practice of yoga, mindfulness and meditation simply as yoga, for the purpose of cultivating straightforwardness.

2.3. Consequences of Incarceration

The Prisons Strategy White Paper, issued by the Ministry of Justice and the former justice secretary Dominic Raab (2021) states the purpose of prison is to protect the public by taking dangerous criminals off the streets and interrupting illegal activity from inside prisons, whilst ensuring the order and discipline of an offender. The White Paper also suggests that tackling the underlying causes of offending and promoting rehabilitation and reform to reduce reoffending is one of the main purposes of our prison system in the UK (Ministry of Justice, 2021). Having said this, an offender may be negatively impacted by incarceration thus presenting risk factors, despite the government's stance on reform and rehabilitation to reduce recidivism. In conjunction with the socioeconomic factors relating to the Good Lives Model perspective of offending that affect an offender and reoffending rates, an individual's health is likely to impact their time in prison and subsequent release, that is to say, prison populations disproportionately reflect the most deprived and marginalised communities where physical and mental health problems are greater than that of the general population (Heard, 2019). It should be noted that this research report will not seek to cover all the consequences associated with incarceration, but those it deems most relevant to the use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation in prisons.

2.3.1 Mental Health

Prisons and those held within these facilities reflect distinct deprivations and this may contribute to further ill health, decreasing an offender's chance of returning to society in a good condition to rebuild and reform (De Viggiani, 2007). There are risk factors such as mental health issues linked with criminal behaviours, with many prisoners presenting with mental health conditions such as anger, depression, bipolar disorder, stress and anxiety, schizophrenia and psychosis (Heard, 2019). Furthermore, many western prisons utilise segregation or isolation as a method of punishment in prison, which can inflict further psychological harm on offenders (Brown, 2020), furthering the mental health issues they may have. In addition, self-harm and suicide is prevalent in prison as a consequence of incarceration. In 2021/2022, there were 684 self-harm incidents per 1,000 prisoners and 75 deaths by suicide per 1000 prisoners in the same year (UK Government, 2022). Researchers are aware of the high levels of mental health morbidity among prisoners, with suicide rates at three times higher than that of the general population (Forrester and Slade, 2013). There is also data to suggest that offenders who have been recently released from prison are at a higher risk of attempting suicide than those still in prison within a year of release (Heard, 2019), perhaps due to a lack of help they could have received to treat a mental illness. The House of Commons Justice Committee (2021) state that an accurate depiction of the magnitude of ill mental health in prisons is absent, with the Ministry of Justice admitting it had a very small amount of information regarding mental illness in prison. It is also unclear how much money is spent on treatment for mental health issues and whether the money is well spent on treatments (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2021). Those who find themselves incarcerated and also suffering with a serious mental illness tend to reoffend at higher rates than those who do not suffer from mental illness (Matejkowski and Ostermann, 2015), suggesting a correlation between ill mental health and reoffending.

2.3.2 Physical Health

Moreover, the ill physical health of an offender in prison is higher than that of the general population (Semenza and Grosholz, 2019). Although not much is known about the impact of poor physical health on behaviour in prison, one line of research has found that ill physical health affects an individual's criminal involvement and the onset of offending (Semenza and Grosholz, 2019). Offenders have presented with physical ailments ranging from back pain and asthma (Stewart et al. 2015) to more serious physical conditions such as a higher prevalence of diabetes, heart disease and cancer in prisons than that of the overall population (Heard, 2019), however it is worth noting here that the extent to which prison itself raises the risk of physical illness requires further investigation as it is of an unknown relation to most physical disorders (Fazel and Baillargeon, 2011). It is within the view of the criminal justice system in England that delivering healthcare to prisoners which is equivalent to what they may

receive outside of prison reduces health inequalities and eventually contributes to rehabilitation and the reduction of reoffending (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2016). This means that while both mental and physical health needs are associated with rates of reoffending in prison and post imprisonment (Wallace and Wang, 2020), the justice system is aware of the advantages of implementing accessible health care to all, supporting the notion that there may be room for alternative methods of rehabilitation in the prison system.

2.3.3 Overcrowding

Furthermore, overcrowding in prisons is said to be an important factor to the harm that imprisonment can cause to the health of not only prisoners, but prison officers alike (Heard, 2019). Prison overcrowding presents a problem in that both staff and prisoners are subjected to more violent behaviours, unsanitary conditions and increased stress that affect the mental and physical health of all individuals inside prison walls (MacDonald, 2018). Prisons in the UK have been subject to overcrowding since 1994 (Prison Reform Trust, 2016) with many prisoners locked in their cells for prolonged periods of time with two or more offenders to a cell (HM Inspectorate of Prisons, 2017). This means an offender has limited access to rehabilitative or meaningful activities within a prison due to its overcrowding, as the capacity of activities cannot meet the demand of the volume of prisoners wishing to participate (Van Ginneken et al. 2017), thus rendering the use of rehabilitative methods for offenders a challenging feat. This implies that there are simply not enough rehabilitative measures in place in prison, but it is suggested by (Carlisle and Johnson, 2020) that correctional institutions can reduce overcrowding by providing more choice to the offender regarding how their time in prison is spent in terms of rehabilitative methods. This in turn imparts a greater sense of control and without the use of purposeful ways of coping with feelings such as anger or depression, or engaging in meaningful work, an offender may continue the cycle of recidivism (Semenza and Grosholz, 2019). This also relates to the Good Lives Model and Desistance theory, in that an offender may find happiness in achieving their primary goods and begin to desist from crime (Purvis et al. 2011) when they are able to shift their perceptions by finding a purpose whilst incarcerated.

2.4 Effects of Yoga, Mindfulness & Meditation

As offenders who experience incarceration in prison may suffer from increased health issues, it is essential one recognises the effects yoga has on an individual to understand if the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation might be employed in UK prisons to help to combat reoffending. As a method of mind-body fitness, yogic practices improve one's strength and flexibility, whilst improving one's quality of life and well-being (Woodyard, 2011).

2.4.1 Yoga & the Physical

Various studies have revealed that the physical effects of yogic practice in relation to physical health is beneficial when used as alternative therapy (Auty et al. 2015). These physiological benefits of practicing yoga include the reduction of back and neck pain and improving back infirmity (Björk Brämberg et al. 2017). Yoga does this by boosting muscle strength and flexibility, with the use of less pain relief medications (Harvard Health Publishing, 2019). In addition, regular practice may increase an individual's cardiovascular endurance (Büssing et al. 2012), that is to say, regular practice shows an increase in baroreflex sensitivity (baroreceptor functions are to sense pressure changes by responding to changes in the arterial walls) with a decrease in impulses from the sympathetic nervous system, thus re-establishing a normal blood pressure level in those who reported hypertension (Devasena and Narhare, 2011). Yoga may aid further in the improvement of balance, functional abilities and may also assist with weight loss, although further study is needed in this area for definitive answers (Büssing et al. 2012). The effect of yoga on an individual's physical health is of significance to the prison populace as the lifestyle of a prisoner may forcibly include less activity (Auty et al. 2015).

2.4.2 Yoga & the Psychological

Further to the physical health of an individual, the mental or psychological benefits of yogic practice may be observed. As a holistic practice which incorporates relations of the mind and the body, yoga may be used as a method of managing depression and anxiety (Cramer et al. 2013), a mental health problem that, this report has suggested, a disproportionate number of offenders in prison struggle with. Usual treatment of depression consists of psychotherapy and medication in the form of antidepressants or a combination of the two, although many individuals do not partake in treatment due to personal choice, side effects of medication or less access to treatment (Bridges and Sharma, 2017). Yoga's effect on depression and anxiety is positive in that it may promote an increase in chemicals within the brain that are lower in individuals with depression, reducing overall symptoms (Beauford, 2017). The meditative aspects of yogic practice may also help to lessen contemplation of negative thoughts and feelings (rumination), by providing an alternate focus for an individual (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). Furthermore, yoga may be seen as a more effective treatment for depression and anxiety than that of antidepressant medication (Beauford, 2017).

Moreover, the use of yoga may be utilised to manage stress and anger. A study conducted by Barrett (2016) found that the use of yoga as an alternative to imprisonment impacts young offenders positively in their rehabilitation with many participants reporting feeling less stressed, more relaxed, less anxious and improved emotional regulation, particularly with managing the emotions of frustration and anger, whilst also grasping the ability to respond to stressful situations in a more mindful way. In addition,

another study conducted by Adhirkari (2021) measured the effect of yogic practice on the aggression of fifty male adolescents. The study found that yoga aided in the reduction of stress and aggression (Adhirkari, 2021). The findings from the studies of adolescents suggest that yogic practices may be used for adolescents and adults alike to aid in the healing of the mind and body.

2.4.3 Yoga & Substance Abuse

It has also been found that yoga may be beneficial for those who battle with substance addictions, although it is worth noting that the validation surrounding this notion is rather narrow (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). Having said this, a study conducted in India by Devi et al. (2014) measured the effectiveness of yoga on depression and quality of life in substance abusers to which it concluded that yogic practice does in fact aid in the reduction of depressive symptoms and increased quality of life in those who abuse drugs. This is definitive with the effects of yoga that this report has explored, suggesting that the reduction in depression may lead to less substance abuse and in turn, less recidivism. In addition, the use of yogic practice as treatment or rehabilitation has been understood to decrease addictive behaviours in an individual, although it is not exactly clear how these mechanisms work (Walia et al. 2021).

Yogic practices can be utilised to inhibit or at the very least, ease emotional or spiritual pain, decrease irritability or stress and incite feelings of relaxation and peace (Woodyard, 2011), primary goods that may allow an individual to attain their goals as the Good Lives Model suggests (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). Furthermore, desistence can be achieved once an individual encourages the therapeutic and rehabilitative processes that yoga can incite (Deuchar, 2016). When contemplating the benefits of this practice in relation to offenders and those who reoffend, there is a well-defined potential for the employment of accredited yoga practice in the prison system (Auty et al. 2015), particularly in the UK to help to tackle reoffending.

Chapter 3: Comparing Rehabilitation Programmes

3.1 Methods of Rehabilitation in Prison

Methods of offender rehabilitation in UK prisons have been subject to the assumption that nothing works in the rehabilitation of a society's offenders over the years (Weisburd et al. 2017). An offender may have one or numerous difficulties related to their offending behaviours, perhaps socioeconomic or psychological issues, thus it is imperative that interventions relating to the Good Lives Model and Desistance theory support the offenders needs to reduce or prevent reoffending. As one looks toward the current methods of rehabilitation, in addition to the vocational and educational support available to most prisoners in the UK, all prisoners maintain their right to health care (Hutchings and Davies, 2021). In 2006, all prisoners became patients of the NHS for the first time, where expanded funding for mental health services in prison was apparent (Piper et al. 2019) and the use of multimodal interventions seeks to address an offender's issues in a holistic (treatment of the individual as a whole, taking all factors of being into account) manner (Ministry of Justice, 2013).

3.1.1 Offending Behaviour Programmes

In England and Wales, offending behaviour programmes and interventions are currently accessible to offenders. These programmes and interventions intend to transform the thinking, attitudes and behaviours of an offender that might lead them to reoffend, incorporating skills aimed at developing pro-social targets for an offender's future, such as problem solving, perspective taking, selfmanagement and relationship management (Ministry of Justice and HM Prison and Probation Service, 2022), including the reduction of impulsive behaviours (Ministry of Justice, 2013). On a short-term basis, offending behaviour programmes have an impact upon offenders with greater needs when delivered regularly (Blud et al. 2010), however, there are aspects that influence the success of a programme, such as the quality of the programme and its delivery, a participant's response to treatment and the risk factors and lifestyle of a participant (Friendship et al. 2010) which should not be ignored. In addition, research has shown that offenders who do not complete an offending behaviour programme they are enrolled in have a higher chance of reoffending once released from prison when compared with those who completed their programmes (Breedvelt et al. 2014). There are currently nineteen accredited programmes of varying natures for prisons and their offenders. Of these programmes, some impart the use of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy or CBT as it is commonly known, depending on the kind of treatment it offers. CBT is a talking therapy that is generally used to treat

depression or anxiety, not dissimilar to yogic practice, dealing with current problems rather than issues from an individual's past (NHS, 2022). It is a rehabilitative method that addresses criminogenic needs with the sturdiest evidence base for reducing rates of reoffending (Scottish Government, 2015). CBT for an offender aims to focus on the criminal thinking that promotes the undertaking of criminal behaviours and generally, evidence indicates that CBT can help to reduce crime (College of Policing, 2018).

3.1.2 Scandinavia & Rehabilitation

While these methods are tried and true and perhaps deemed of some use, it is here one must consider the options for rehabilitative methods in place to tackle reoffending for UK prisoners and ask, what are the alternatives to alleviate mental and physical pressures to aid in the rehabilitation of offenders? Countries with lower reoffending rates than that of the UK, namely Scandinavian countries such as Norway and Sweden, adopt a less punitive approach to punishment than the UK or USA (Sterbenz, 2014). Rehabilitation of an offender is the most prevalent goal of incarceration in Scandinavia, with decisions regarding criminal justice policy often made by published criminologists and academics, thus unaffected by political interventions (Fowler, 2015). Prison policy in these countries is based on results the prisons produce, not the costs, these differing factors allowing for the existence of open prisons (Fowler, 2015). Furthermore, as the conditions of prisons Nordic countries have become more open, the rates of crime and subsequent reoffending seem to have decreased (Denny, 2016). As the emphasis placed on the use of prison here is offender rehabilitation, the purpose of punishment in Nordic countries for those who question the openness of these prisons is the loss of liberty for an offender (Denny, 2016), which shows that incarceration is still an exertion of punitive measures. When a prisoner in Norway is serving a sentence, the offenders still observe the same, equal rights to that of a Norwegian citizen, retaining a sense of normality for a serving prisoner (Tønseth et al. 2019). Furthermore, a prison officers' role in Nordic prison is seen as that of a disciplinarian and also as a social worker, who's duty it is to stabilise behaviour while preparing prisoners for re-entry to the community and ultimately aiding in the reduction of reoffending (Akhtar, 2020). With these differences in mind, alternative methods of rehabilitation in prison in Scandinavian countries, contrary to those commonly offered in the UK, include the use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation, a required practice for all those incarcerated, with the Swedish Prison and Probation Service offering this class since 2008 (Sfendla et al. 2018) It is worth mentioning here that while the use of yoga, mindfulness and meditation holds a predominant place in Scandinavian prisons, other countries such as Canada, Israel, India, Australia and the US have introduced yoga into their rehabilitative methods as an informal means to aid the reduction of reoffending in the respective countries (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). This research has found that in

the UK, a charity known as The Prison Phoenix Trust offers meditation and yoga classes to approximately eighty secure establishments in the UK (The Prison Phoenix Trust, 2020). As such, this report will utilise this finding to answer its hypothesis.

3.2 And the Costs?

Budget and monetary matters have been of keen interest to governmental bodies with financial incentives offered to private companies who are willing to employ previously incarcerated persons (Bell, 2013). In saying this, a prison should work toward being a cost efficient method that focuses on the rehabilitation of its inhabitants (Steer et al. 2016) however, it is suggested by Barker (2013) that the social, moral and economic costs of prisons have generated more social problems than they have reduced, with some costs going unreported (McBride, 2013). This, therefore, means that prison may not be an effective method of rehabilitation, rather that the interventions in place can aid in its efficacy, but the costs of said interventions must come under scrutiny for policy makers.

3.2.1 Cost of Imprisonment

The cost of a prison place per year for offenders in the UK between 2016 and 2017 was approximately £38,042 (Ministry of Justice, 2017). Between 2020 and 2021, the cost per prison place stood at £48,162, with the cost per prisoner standing at £48,409 (Ministry of Justice, 2022). This may be compared with the cost per prisoner in Sweden, who's rate of recidivism stands at 20% (Aidoo, 2016), which in 2015, was on average of \$91,000 (Shenigo, 2015). At the current exchange rate, this looks more like £75,000 on average per prisoner. This figure presents a difference of £26,591, which is relatively high when matched with the UK, but rehabilitation and penal ideology in Sweden being of a rehabilitative and far less punitive nature shows that imparting funds into prisons for the purposes of rehabilitation is a conducive factor to implementing rehabilitative methods and lessening reoffending. The rise in costs per prison place and cost per prisoner is, in part, due to the growth of the prison population (Focus Prisoner Education, 2023), that is to say, the more people incarcerated and the more time an offender spends imprisoned, the greater the monetary or economic cost. Considering this, it is within the states interest to reflect upon alternatives to imprisonment (Ismail, 2019) and to methods of rehabilitation when an offender is in prison to aid in the reduction of reoffending.

3.2.2 Cost of Reoffending

Reoffending in the UK, specifically England and Wales costs around £18.1 billion a year, with the approximate cost of reoffending by adults standing at £16.7 billion a year (Newton et al. 2019). To break this figure down further, the cost of reoffences committed by adults who had previously served a

custodial sentence of less than twelve months was £5 billion whereas reoffending for those who served a custodial sentence of twelve months or more cost £1 billion (Newton et al. 2019). This suggests that shorter custodial sentences do not have as much of an effect on prisoner reoffending as longer sentences, with shorter sentences having a consistent association with greater levels of reoffending (Mews et al. 2015). If other interventions were to be employed, there would be an approximate economic cost benefit of £490 million (Newton et al. 2019), affirming a cost efficacy for the deployment of alternative methods of rehabilitation to help to tackle reoffending amongst UK prisoners.

3.2.3 Cost of Rehabilitation

There is evidence to suggest that alternatives to prison and alternate interventions are more beneficial at reducing a person’s predisposition to offend after a completed custodial sentence (Newton et al. 2019). The table below shows the most cost effective interventions and the moderately cost effective interventions within UK prisons currently used to rehabilitate offenders:

	Accountability	Long-term Behavior Change	Accountability & Long-term Behavior Change	Stabilisation
Most cost effective	Electronic monitoring Home confinement Probation Offense specific classes	Cognitive behavior programming Skill based supervision	Intensive supervised probation with treatment	Work release Housing search assistance Outpatient mental health services & medication
Moderately cost effective	Pretrial supervision with other services Day reporting with monitoring Supervised work crews Restorative justice Intensive supervised probation Restitution	Drug/alcohol treatment Sex offender treatment Therapeutic communities Jobs Vocational ed. Academic ed. Mentoring	Drug, alcohol, mental health & wellness courts Therapeutic day reporting	Housing Supportive housing

Figure 2. Image to show the most cost-effective alternatives to incarceration (from Steer et al. 2016).

When one considers the table above, one of interventions deemed to be the most cost-effective method of rehabilitation to target long-term behavioural changes is Cognitive behaviour programming (Steer et al. 2016) or in other words, CBT, however, no reviews have reported any information about costs or cost benefits of CBT programmes in the UK (College of Policing, 2018). Interventions to aid in the rehabilitation of offenders that are offered by psychologists or psychiatrists come at a steep price, with inaccessibility being a key issue, although it is other methods of rehabilitation that aid in targeting behavioural change, such as yoga, mindfulness and meditation and not dissimilar to the aims of CBT,

that might be employed as a more cost effective method of rehabilitation (Bilderbeck et al. 2013) to help to combat reoffending in UK prisons.

Although a cost-benefit analysis for yogic practices in prison is yet to be studied, a cost-benefit analysis has been produced for transcendental meditation. The analysis conducted by Magill (2008) found that savings in US correctional institutions are expected to occur after the addition of transcendental meditation programmes in prison due to reduced reoffending rates, reduced medical expenditures, a more governable prison setting and an improved quality of life for prison officers. The analysis found that transcendental meditation may have a cost-benefit ratio of 1:8.5, indicating that for every dollar expended on transcendental meditation in some US prisons, a saving of \$8.50 would be made, with a saving of 46% arising in institutions and a saving of 54% occurring for the public (Derlic, 2020). With the savings potentially generated by transcendental meditation, it is possible that the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation in UK prisons can yield similar results for costs to the state and the public, ultimately aiding in the reduction of reoffending, although much more research is needed to definitively conclude the cost-benefits of yogic practice.

3.3 Yoga in Correctional Settings

To truly gauge whether the addition of yoga, mindfulness and meditation may be employed in UK prisons as an alternative method of rehabilitation to help to combat reoffending, it is imperative to consider past studies conducted within this realm and organisations that currently employ yogic practice in prisons to determine its efficacy. The research within this field is extremely limited, however this research will acknowledge two studies that have been conducted in Sweden and the UK, countries that have differing penal approaches, to support the idea that yoga might in fact be applied as an accredited method of rehabilitation for offenders to reduce the potential for future reoffending.

3.3.1 A Summary of Past Prison Yoga Studies

Bilderbeck et al. (2013) studied the effects of British prisoners' involvement in a 10-week yoga course, specifically whether it develops behavioural control and reduced psychological distress. Piloted in seven prisons in the West Midlands, this study combined self-reporting measures and a cognitive behavioural task in 45 participants randomly allocated to prison yoga classes and 55 participants allocated to a control group who were asked to continue their day-to-day activities and exercise, with both groups asked to monitor their physical movement both inside and outside of the study. In conjunction, a post intervention questionnaire was undertaken with the participants one week after completion of the yoga course in addition to a cognitive behavioural task, measuring stress, impulsivity and psychological

distress (Bilderbeck et al. 2013). The study found that on the whole, prisoners who participated in the yoga classes experienced increased mood and better performance in cognitive-behavioural assignments and decreased stress and psychological distress compared to the control group (Bilderbeck et al. 2013). The study successfully substantiates the findings of the limited literature regarding yoga in prisons, in that yogic practice can improve an individual's psychological wellbeing as well as improve sleep, mood and social behaviour (Bilderbeck et al. 2013). In addition, the use of a small but diverse sample, from differing prison security levels to race, marital status, age and severity of offence, shows that the results of this study might be generalisable to a larger population of prisoner in Britain (Bilderbeck et al. 2013) and thus the UK. While data was gathered from Category B prisons and below, due to legal limitations, the researchers were not able to test the effects of yogic practice upon Category A prisoners (Bilderbeck et al. 2013) which leaves room for future research upon the effects of yoga in prisons among those who are considered extremely dangerous. Furthermore, specificity in relation to the elements of yogic practice or different forms of yoga used in prison that observe benefits in a prisoner's overall wellbeing is lacking (Bilderbeck et al. 2013) meaning this study does not hone into the particular facets of yogic practice that might benefit an individual, rather it looks at yoga as a whole. This research would argue that this is a useful way to study the effect of yoga upon criminogenic behaviour and risk factors, for as this research has stated, yoga, mindfulness and meditation yield the greatest benefits from combinations of each. Despite the limitations, this study found evidence to suggest that yogic practice may have significant impact on the mood and psychological wellbeing, promoting the primary goods of incarcerated members of the population, thus revealing the potential accredited use for yoga in UK prisons to ultimately aid in the reduction of reoffending amongst the UK prison populace.

Moreover, Kerekes et al. (2017) explored whether 10 weeks of yoga classes in prison may have an association with higher levels of positivity, impulse control, psychological well-being and improved quality of sleep and lower levels of stress and aggression. This study was conducted in nine medium and high security prisons in Sweden, including two facilities that housed female inmates between November 2013 and July 2015, however data gathering from the female facilities ended in January 2015 due to lack of participation (Kerekes et al. 2017). The final sample size was 152 participants who were randomly allocated to either a yoga group, following particular guidelines for prison yoga classes devised by Bilderbeck et al. (2013) and participating in weekly 90-minute yoga practices with a teacher, or a control group, where participants were added to a waiting list and asked to undertake other forms of physical activity for the same amount of time each week (Kerekes et al. 2017). The study found that yoga practice in Swedish prison is indeed associated with increased positive emotional well-being, with

calm, relaxed and content states of being increasing and hostile, nervous and unhappy states decreasing (Kerekes, et al. 2017). This study made use of randomised control trials, which is considered as the standard metric for clinical trials, to which the researchers consider this a strength of their research (Kerekes et al. 2017). In addition, attrition is a concern for many a researcher and Kerekes et al. (2017) note that participant attrition was significant, at 32.7%, but this number was not as high as Bilderbeck et al. (2013) participant attrition rate, which was approximately 40%. This number can perhaps be attributed to prisoner request, with a participants age being a contributing factor to both studies (Kerekes et al. 2017). Participants of this study reported a decrease in antisocial behaviours and subsequent outcomes of those behaviours when compared with the control group, with Kerekes et al. (2017) suggesting the relationship between yogic practice in addressing the criminogenic needs of antisocial behaviours to be of significant interest. Yogic practice can therefore serve as a tool that may help re-integrate an offender back into the community upon their release, spurring a reduction in the risks of reoffending (Kerekes et al. 2017) and aiding in an offender desisting from criminal behaviours.

Furthermore, both studies cited above have noted the importance of a yoga teacher when conducting studies regarding yoga practice in prison, to which this factor can be seen as both a strength and a limitation for past and future study. There may likely be variations in the way classes are taught, the length of classes, differing interpretations of yoga and the styles of yogic practice being taught to the prison population and which actions may yield the most benefit (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016). In addition, some teachers might be more engaging than others or might perhaps teach poses that impact a class in differing ways, thus impacting the outcome of a practice (Derlic, 2020). This means that a consensus must be reached when studying yoga in prison on the type of yogic practice imparted in prison and what level of experience a chosen teacher has (Derlic, 2020).

3.3.2 Prison Yoga from the Inside

Further to the quantitative nature of studies past that show that yogic practice can help to address some consequences of incarceration, it is important to acknowledge how prison yoga practices impact a prisoner from the perspective of a prisoner. The Prison Yoga Project (2023) and The Prison Phoenix Trust (2020), charities that provide yoga in prison in US, Swedish and some UK prisons, both provide testimonials from offenders who have taken part in prison yoga practices and how they feel with regards to these practices, some of which are as follows:

“I feel like a different person. I wish I had known about this when I was on the outside. Now I can honestly say I will never come to prison again” (The Prison Phoenix Trust, 2020, online).

“This class allows you to learn and grow in positive ways that allow you to feel normal. That you can do normal things that are outside of the criminal lifestyle and drug culture. And that is the first step to building a better life. I may not be able to fix the world at large, but I can work on myself to be a more positive and productive person”, (Prison Yoga Project, 2023, online).

“For the first time I’m looking at the bigger picture. What did I really believe my future held for my family and those around me? I have never questioned my lifestyle before, never said ‘Is this the last time? I won’t be back. This isn’t the life for me,” (The Prison Phoenix Trust, 2020, online).

These testimonials, in conjunction with the evidence and conclusions past studies have provided, show a great deal of support for prison yoga practices upon the physical and mental welfare of an offender and encourage the notion that yogic practice may aid the reduction of reoffending. There is an innate need within prisons and secure establishments to implement an alternative to current rehabilitative methods that are less expensive and that may extend to a large portion of the prison populace, aiding in the achievement of primary goods as the Good Lives Model suggests and desistance from crime, although it should be noted that further research is required to guarantee that yoga, mindfulness and meditation practices within prisons can accomplish the required results (Muirhead and Fortune, 2016), that is, to overcome risk factors of UK prisoners to help to combat reoffending.

Chapter 4: Conclusion

To conclude, this research report sought to provide evidence that yoga, mindfulness and meditation may be employed in UK prisons to help to tackle reoffending by considering criminological theories of rehabilitation to gain an academic insight into the field of rehabilitation in prisons, then looking at the population to which this research pertains, the consequences prison has upon an individual and the methods already in place in prison that might help to rehabilitate an offender to support or disprove the notion put forth. It was vital for this project to review the existing literature within this field, providing secondary analysis of the efficacy of yogic practice upon the consequences of prison, whilst considering the costs of rehabilitation in prison.

This research report found that there is a vast array of consequences that an individual might experience, both physical and mental, which need to be addressed to lessen the rate of recidivism, in addition to the methods in place that address the socio-economic factors pertaining to criminogenic needs. Methods currently available in UK prisons to address these factors relate more so to worked-based training and education to enable an offender to reintegrate into society in the hopes that they may not reoffend. Drug misuse, a lack of education and unemployment may cause an individual to offend and subsequently reoffend once released from prison, however, offenders who are imprisoned may suffer consequences of incarceration. Some of the consequences this project has addressed, take the form of mental and physical health concerns, which if gone unchecked, hold a correlation to reoffending. When imprisoned, an offender may experience back pain and asthma, although more research is required to gauge the extent to which prison may affect one's physical health. Overcrowding may also affect the mental health of an individual. Offenders may present with conditions such as depression, anger, stress, anxiety and bipolar disorder, with self-harm and suicide of particular prevalence among the prison population. This is where Cognitive Behavioural Therapy may benefit an offender as it aims to treat depression and anxiety and by extension, reduce reoffending, however, Scandinavian prisons, falling under a justice system that presents some distinct differences in the way justice is deployed, including an emphasis on offender rehabilitation, the observation of equal rights, the training of prison officers to act as social workers as well as enforcers and a prison policy that is centred around results not costs and the employment of alternative methods of rehabilitation, that of yoga, mindfulness and meditation, to which it can be argued, treat the aforementioned 'disorders' in a holistic way. Yoga, mindfulness and meditation involves pulling one's attention to the present moment through a series of movement, poses (asanas) and breathwork, yielding mental and physical benefits,

including less back and neck pain, improved flexibility, lowered blood pressure, decreased stress, anger, anxiety and depression and the increased ability to regulate emotions. As Nordic countries have a recidivism rate of 20% which is one of the lowest rates of reoffending in the world, exploring the use of yogic practice in prisons is a justified feat. The cost per prison place in Nordic prisons is significantly more when compared with the UK. At the time of this research, the monetary difference stood at £26,591, but there is no figure to suggest how much is spent on yoga in Scandinavian prisons. With cost per prison place continually rising within the UK, this report suggests that employing the use of yogic practice within UK prison may benefit an offender in a meaningful way at an assumed lower cost to the state.

It is suggested that the use of yogic practice implies a continuity of care, in that, where an individual may not be able to access the care they may require to address criminogenic needs, arm the offender with a basis for yogic practice so that they are able to practice yoga once released from prison, which will then incite a clear potential for the reduction of reoffending. The use of yoga in prison adheres to the notions of theoretic explanations of rehabilitation, most notably the Good Lives Model and Desistance theory, both of which suggest that an offender may shape their own perceptions to attain their primary goods in a socially acceptable way after successful rehabilitation and live a life free of criminal activity. Based on the findings of this research report, namely the benefits that yoga, mindfulness and meditation, this research chose to omit the observing of factors such as race, gender and age in the hopes that the findings may be implied for all offenders, not just one demographic. Further research should consider the lack of research in the area and perhaps include a longitudinal study exploring the potential for yogic practice in the UK to aid in a reduction of reoffending, whilst considering the demographics of prison populations in the UK to add more value to the literature available.

“The walls could hold their bodies, but nothing could imprison their souls – except their own minds”, (Singer, 2015. p.121)

List of Figures

Figure 1. Image to show asana poses (from Bilderbeck et al. 2013).

Figure 2. Image to show the most cost-effective alternatives to incarceration (from Steer et al. 2016).

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